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THEORETICAL APPROACHES ON THE FORMATION OF ELECTRONIC GOVERNMENT

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the study of theoretical approaches on the stages of electronic government development. For this purpose, the approaches of native and foreign scientists have been analyzed in the research work. Also, the results of the research of some prestigious international organizations regarding the development stages of e-government and the factors affecting its formation have also been investigated. The important mechanisms of e-government technologies have been listed, as well as the advantages obtained due to the operation of e-government are summarized.

Keywords: E-government, ICT, state, stage, network, service.

Introduction

In the modern world we live in one of the main directions in public administration is e-government. At this time of rapid development of ICT e-government has a great importance in the realization of the necessity of reconstruction of mutual relations between states and citizens. Thus, this process ensures people with efficient and accessible services provided by government. At the same time, application of ICT and its widespread usage increases transparency, accountability and citizen participation in public administration.

Theoretical approaches on the formation of e-government

E-government has gone through several stages in order to reach its current level. Different approaches have been proposed regarding the number and types of these stages. We are going to analyze ideas of native and foreign scientists:

A.D.Huseynova assumes that electronic government goes through 4 stages in its evolution process: existence stage, interactive stage, transaction stage and renewal stage [4, p.69].

Other scientists also present four-stage model in the formation process of e-government: information placement stage, feedback-interactive interaction stage, transaction stage and transformation stage of state structure [12; 14].

However, G.A.Kulkayev and his coauthors claim 6 stages in the process of electronic government formation:

- ✓ formation of information portals in public administration;
- ✓ creation of state-population, state-business and state-state communication channels;
- ✓ automation of the process of providing public services;
- ✓ ensuring the work of state data processing centers;
- ✓ application of big data analysis system for prediction and planning of development;
- ✓ gradual transfer of decision-making authorities on simple issues to the neural network [6, p.9].

According to the approach of other researchers, the formation of e-government takes a long time and this process goes through 4 stages [21, p.158]:

✚ the first stage covering the years 2000-2005.

In this period, electronic government is reflected in the network as a state. At this stage all the information needed by the citizens is placed on the state websites. Services to the population are provided offline with minimal use of ICT.

✚ the second stage covering the years 2005-2010. In this period electronic government gradually moves to the second stage. At this stage, mutual relations between citizens and government bodies are performed online, the use of ICT is expanding, interaction is carried out through e-mail and special state websites. Documentation is done electronically, but most government services are provided using the old model. It is for the reason that citizens are just beginning to use new technologies.

✚ the third stage covering the years 2010-2012. Electronic government is more represented in the network, most services are provided online, electronic authentication is emerging.

✚ the fourth stage covering the years 2012-2015. At this stage transformation of a complex system emerges, an all-encompassing government is established and services to the population are served via a single site by several departments and gradually transforming according to the network principle [11, pp.120-135].

World experience shows that the sequence of these stages is not required in the establishment of electronic government.

The researches of a several prestigious international organizations regarding the development stages of e-government, as well as the factors affecting its formation are of great importance.

According to the version by the United Nations (UN), 5 stages are distinguished in the evolution process of electronic government. These are: Emerging Presence, Enhanced Presence, Interactive Presence, Transactional Presence and Networked Presence stages.

In the stage of *Emerging Presence*, the work of state structures is one-sided, citizens provided by the information even in a limited form. Information is not transferred from citizens to state structures. Limited information is displayed on rarely updated websites. Various ministries and organizations create information

pages where they place information about themselves. At this stage, portals created by state bodies are not combined into a single portal.

In the stage of *Enhanced Presence* documents and normative acts posted on the created sites can be obtained.

In the stage of *Interactive Presence* it is possible to transfer protected files and establish mutual relations with citizens. It becomes possible to use e-mail and electronic digital signature. The sites are updated regularly.

In the stage of *Transactional Presence* online transactions are carried out, including issuing documents, payments, etc.

In the fifth stage called *Networked Presence* services are integrated to provide knowledge, information and services, as well as forums, surveys and consultations with citizens can be conducted online [20, p.13].

Scientific researches conducted by the UN, the World Bank (WB), the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) and other international organizations on the development of e-government have revealed the important role of a number of factors. Conventionally, these factors can be divided into 5 groups [1, pp.347-348]:

1. The first group of factors characterizes the characteristics of technical development. Security, privacy and infrastructure status are among these mentioned features. It is the success of economic and technological development that creates the basic conditions for the formation of e-government.

As a result of one of the studies based on the evaluations conducted by applying the correlation method in the sample of 150 countries, it was concluded that there is a positive and close relationship between the online services index, which measures the quality of services provided by the state, and the Electronic participation index, which studies the level of use of electronic services by the population. Based on the analysis, it can be concluded that the countries with a high score in the online services index have a strong online service infrastructure. In order to improve provision of services by governments digital technologies are widely used in the developed countries (eg. Finland, the USA, Japan, Estonia, South Korea, Singapore, New Zealand, Australia).

However, at the current development stage of digital transformation there are still countries that can not provide accessible, secure services and they can not provide people with the effectively useage of digital technologies. These are mainly underdeveloped, poor countries with a low standard of living (for example, Somalia, Afghanistan, the Democratic Republic of the Congo, Sudan, the Democratic People's Republic of Korea, the Central African Republic, Eritrea) [16, pp.42-43; p.55].

2. The second group of factors includes financial resources. Design and implementation of many projects related to technological development, especially large-scale reforms, mainly depends on technological possibilities. Thus, there is a positive correlation between the level of countries' income and the Electronic Government Development Index (EGDI): the EGDI index of

high-income countries is higher than of low-income countries [9, p.13].

Some researchers also [5, pp.31-52; 19, p.429] note the correlation between country's economic development and the level of development of e-government. However, "even countries with limited resources can succeed in the development of e-government and providing online services if they are supported in other ways (for example, by wise leadership, a favorable political environment or by international cooperation)" [9, p.24]. Even in countries with a low Online Service Index (OSI) there is progress in the provision of these services. Thus, the number of online services provided in countries with a low OSI level increased from 1 in 2018 to 4.5 in 2022. In these countries mainly 5 services are provided online: registering a business, applying for a building permit, applying for a birth, death or marriage certificate [10, p.26].

Liu Zhenmin, Deputy Secretary General of the UN notes that, although the e-government development rating correlates with a country's income level, financial resources are not the only factor. Here, of course, strategic leadership and commitment to advanced electronic services is of great importance [10].

3. The third group includes organizational-management factors. Thus, support of a high-level management hierarchy, resistance to the transition to electronic forms at work, or a favorable attitude, the presence of professional staff and trainers, an ideal infrastructure of mutual relations and general management principles between agencies and departments, etc. such issues belong to this group.

4. The fourth group includes social and socio-cultural factors. These factors indicate the possibilities of using electronic services by groups with different interests and by numerous people. Factors included into this group reflect people's cultural level, differences in income and education, the presence or absence of "digital divide", and misunderstanding of consumer needs and expectations.

As the UN Deputy Secretary-General Li Junhua noted, "in connection with the COVID-19 pandemic, in the last two years, 90% of member states have created special portals for the provision of public services and problem solving or have reserved space on their national portals" [10]. The COVID-19 pandemic has shown the current state of affairs in this field as litmus paper, once again proving that e-government plays an important role in providing public services and innovation services. For all these reasons, in modern times, the application of innovation methods in healthcare, online education, employment and communication (contact) issues in regulation and solution is increasing year by year [10].

5. The fifth group includes factors that indicate the characteristics of political institutions and government organizations. It is political institutions and government organizations that determine the openness or closeness of the decisions made, the accountability of the government and whether it helps or hinders development. This group of factors shows the quality of public sphere regulation and state self-management. It is these last two factors that allow determining the perspective of the development of e-government.

Although the role of these factors mentioned above in the formation of e-government is clearly visible, in this field there are a number of other factors of importance which are neglected. For instance, state structure and degree of centralization. Thus, the most developed countries (for example, Denmark, Estonia, the Republic of Korea, Singapore) in the establishment of e-government are not very large, and they are unitary and highly technologically developed countries.

However, in countries with federal governance and significant decentralization these processes are slow and complicated for a number of reasons: agreeing on decisions on e-government requires additional efforts and time, interactions between different bodies of government, as well as a number of issues need to be agreed at all levels. Such factors have led to relatively slow formation of e-government in a highly developed country like Germany. However, the high level of e-government in federal countries like the USA and Australia show that this factor does not always play a decisive role [1, p.348].

It should be noted that the influence of countries' political regimes and level of democracy on the formation of e-government is not entirely clear. Surely, in the establishment of e-government successful results are achieved in democratic countries. Hence, in these countries the authorities prefer transparent and interactive relations with citizens in their interactions. However, in the last decade even in countries with autocratic regime, technological innovation in governance and additional tools in the fight against corruption are used. Normally, China and the Persian Gulf countries are set as an example in the rapid development of e-government [17, p.554].

Advantages of e-government

Several important mechanisms of e-government technologies attract attention:

➤ The first is the formation of electronic document circulation. Establishment of electronic management system-IDM (Integrated Document management) with the help of technologies.

➤ The second is establishment of a single authentication and authorization system that gives equal rights to all electronic government participants.

➤ The third is stimulating citizen initiative and citizen participation in the development and implementation of state decisions and creating an appropriate platform.

➤ The fourth is forming an all-encompassing government that provides public services through a single window. The single portal is one of the most important successes of e-government [3].

Summarizing the results of some researchers, it is possible to group the advantages of electronic government as follows:

- ❖ effective operation of executive bodies increases; administrative and industrial delays related to state apparatus are reduced; expenses spent on inter-organizational interactions are reduced; the transparency of information within the bureaucratic system increases and due to the elimination of "ring" redundancy the intra-organizational opportunism of employees disappears; speed of reaction of the bureaucratic apparatus to the needs of the society increases; management adapts to internal and external conditions and becomes more

flexible, paper workflow is replaced by electronic circulation;

- ❖ the quality of services provided to the population and business increases significantly. Internet technologies reduce transaction delays of population and businesses in services received from government organizations. Also, increasing the speed and the quality of gathering information about consumers' needs lead to the success in this field;

- ❖ The efficiency of the ownership activity of the population and business increases and the cost of information decreases. Information asymmetry causes intervals in the market-based economy. That is why one of the important tasks of government bodies in the terms of the concept of e-government is to help businesses by increasing the transparency of information about the quality of services and goods for all interested parties. One of the important issues is to create information resources for the state, to provide population and business with the necessary information;

- ❖ in order to create public welfare in the society citizens' participation is ensured;

- ❖ unlimited access to the servers at any time of the day;

- ❖ online multi-channel accessibility through various platforms (computer, smartphone, TV) and technologies (internet, mobile communication) is available;

- ❖ secure usage – data protection, verification of the user's data, the possibility of stable feedback;

- ❖ It is possible by the user transparently control the personal data submitted to the standard procedure;

- ❖ easy handling – getting important information conveniently and convenient communication with officials is provided;

- ❖ reduction of corruption occurs due to the minimization of communication with service officials and intermediaries;

- ❖ automation of service provision processes, increasing efficiency of service providers' activities;

- ❖ citizens' desire to participate in public administration increases;

- ❖ the relations between government and citizens are improving at a radical speed;

- ❖ people's satisfaction with public services increases;

- ❖ accessibility to public services by enterprises and population increases;

- ❖ the population's trust in government increases;

- ❖ government institutions increase transparency and accountability in decision-making;

- ❖ the improvement of management mechanisms helps to realize upcoming economic and political goals;

- ❖ supports the realization of reforms implemented in the country;

- ❖ integration of technologies, information and knowledge improves the existing system of internal networks between the state and society, builds new multiple communication networks;

- ❖ helps to achieve success in the areas such as health, education, security and social insurance;

- ❖ also, ICT is expanding to cover all areas of social life [4, pp.69-70; 2, pp.104-109; 8, p.26; 7, p.1504; 13, pp.449-450].

It should be noted that, efficiency of provided public services has a positive effect on the potential of e-government, and the usefulness of e-services is the most important indicator of the efficiency of e-government [18, pp.303-311].

Researches conducted in 191 countries show that, e-government increases the efficiency of national government and strengthens the fight against corruption [15, pp.155-173].

Conclusion

On the whole, I would like to conclude that the purpose of the article is to analyze theoretical attitudes towards the formation of e-government and to research various theories and opinions in this field. The theoretical views included in the research, explain various aspects and goals of the formation of e-government. In the article, the stages of e-government development and advantages obtained as a result of e-government operation were discussed. The stages of e-government development represent the evolution of services provided by the government through ICT.

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